

10 years of RDMO

The Research Data Management Organiser as software and community

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Abstract

Data management plans (DMPs) are a central component of research data management (RDM) and are also mandatory for many research funders in the application process. Data management planning is also becoming increasingly important for the practical implementation of RDM by researchers and is a central tool for training and advising researchers on RDM.

The presentation looks back on the success story of the DMP software 'Research Data Management Organiser' (RDMO), which was developed in two DFG-funded project phases between 2015 and 2020 and subsequently very successfully transferred to an active open source community as described by [1]. Around 60 institutions in Germany (and other European countries) are currently known to be using RDMO. RDMO has clearly established itself as the most widely used software solution for DMP in Germany. In particular, the NFDI basic service DMP4NFDI is also based on RDMO.

The concepts and ideas behind RDMO are presented, the development of the software and the community outlined, the current status presented and a look into the near and distant future. A comparison with other DMP software completes the picture. In particular, it shows how the transformation from a DFG project to a loose community to the founding of the association in 2024 and how and why RDMO is now used by universities and research institutions of all kinds.

In addition to voices from the operating and developing infrastructure institutions, experiences with DMPs and RDMO from research are also shared.

Keywords: data management planning, dmp, Research Data Management Organiser, RDMO, open-source community, success story

Resources

- <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/> RDMO homepage
- <https://github.com/rdmorganiser> RDMO software code
- <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog> RDMO DMP templates
- <https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> RDMO documentation

- <https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/RDMO> RDMO community Wiki
- <https://dmp.services.base4nfdi.de/> RDMO-based NFDI Basic Service “DMP4NFDI”

Author contributions

- Jagusch, Gerald (Writing, Project administration)
- Spenger, Martin (Writing, Project administration)

Competing interests

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References

- [1] Ivonne Anders; Harry Enke; Daniela Adele Hausen; Christin Henzen; Gerald Jagusch; Giacomo Lanza; Olaf Michaelis; Karsten Peters-von Gehlen; Torsten Rathmann; Jürgen Rohrwild; Sabine Schönau; Kerstin Vanessa Wedlich-Zachodin; Jürgen Windeck (2024). **The Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) – a Strong Community Behind an Established Software for DMPs and Much More** [Journal Article]. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-028